

Turo-Turo and Online Market: Essential Problems Established of Purchaser and Retailer

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to determine the essential role of the purchaser and retailer among turo-turo and online market. The growth of turo-turo and online market in developing countries can largely be seen as the good and bad results of the functional progress strategy. The researcher used mix method study including the google form and questionnaire, face to face interview for the owner and note taking. The informants used are the owners of the turo-turo and the owners of the materials in the online market world . The data used are primary data. The researcher used SWOT analysis as an effective way to measure the current status of the retailer in barrios hence this proved that creating a buzz in the industry is online popularity though the essence of the product is standard and the spirit of competition is experienced. Most of the turo-turo are traditionally grown and the availability of their product is easily captured in their surroundings. Thus, it is difficult for them to develop optimally due to the limited human resource quality. There are also obstacles in partnership efforts with the fact that the bigger entrepreneurs tend to dominate the decision making in pricing, product quality, as well as the payment system. This essentials problems established by the retailer and purchaser is just normal in the Philippine Market specific in the barrios. This ascertained that Ilokanos in the Philippines is business minded also in just a small kind of their daily living activity.

Keywords: Turo-Turo, Online Market, Problems Established, Purchaser and Retailer.

I. Introduction

The Filipinos perform to be one of the most industrious citizen in terms of selling foods and materials in living for it will make a change or difference in the life of the consumer or costumer either in the local, national or global stage. This is the very reason why marketer continues to explore variables that will contribute effectively for the good of each party. Turo-turo is a local term for among Filipinos market where accessibility among diasporic like the province of Isabela Philippines particular in Brgy. Rizal. Quirino is located estimated 500 km away from Ilagan City, the provincial capital of Isabela. Quirino, Isabela composed of 21 baranggay more so the center of their turo-turo (market) can be found at Luna, Quirino, and Isabela.

The research focused on the Brgy. Rizal turo-turo vendor. Although they are considered as a less contributive sector to the increase of the national income, the informal sector, including turo-turo. The informal sector in question is units of small scale enterprises that produce and distribute goods and services with an ultimate purpose of creating job opportunities for themselves. In the effort to reach their goal, they face various constraints such as shortage in skill, and in physical and knowledge resources.

The growth of turo-turo and online market in developing countries can largely be seen as the good and bad results of the functional progress strategy. On the constructive point of view, the revenue increase, mainly of the low income class, has led to the higher level of demand for goods produced by the informal sector. Meanwhile, on the bad side, the high number of unemployment in the formal sector, due to the uneven development and industrialization pattern, has forced them to seek for other job opportunities by becoming entrepreneurs.

Researcher used the concept of synergy where is win-win cooperation generated through collaboration between each party without any defeat. According to Covey (2004) in his book-7 Habits of Highly Effective People, it is said that synergy is a condition where $1+1=3$. Synergy is a mutual complementary-relationship to achieve a bigger result. The concept of synergy includes the following: 1. Positive and result oriented 2. Diverse perspectives to replace or complete the paradigm 3. Cooperation and similarity in goal as well as agreement 4. Effective effort in process an example of synergy that can be seen in the world around us is the concept of food courts or food centers. It is an area where food and beverage outlets are gathered to serve the customers, so that they will have various choices of food and drinks to purchase. This effectively increases the outlets' income better than when they stand apart in different places. Synergy can reduce the costs or operational costs without reducing the operating income. The common language in the world of business is budget-sharing. Synergies are a process, and it takes time to establish it. Once successfully built, the synergy will create a creative and innovative cooperation. The researcher used the SWOT analysis in arriving the result of the study.

II. Materials and Method

Research Design

The research object is turo-turo and online market problem established that process any products made of raw materials, foods and accessories. This research is a mixed method study and the researcher also used the Google form. The informants used are the owners of the turo-turo and the owners of the materials of the online market. The data used are primary data. The data are collected by applying in-depth interview and extracting information through focus group discussion (FGD) to find a

more holistic and comprehensive phenomena and questionnaire. Verbal and practical responses such as role playing, speech delivery, and persuasive essay writing. The researcher used descriptive analysis approach is a troubleshooting procedure toward the investigated issues. It is applied by describing the condition of the research subject/object at the present time.

Results and Discussion

The descriptive analysis on the turo-turo and online market-made products in the municipality of Quirino province of Isabela:

Table 1

Summary of open-ended question from strength analysis of Purchaser and Retailer.

STRENGTH ANALYSIS		
Outlook from	Number	Statement
	1	The good relationship between the online marketer and the buyer.
	2	The product direction that has been planned and citizen from local barrios
	3	The selection and construction of a strategic or easily-reached outlet to accommodate the customers that will implement a proper sale process.
	4	The attractive product packaging and the distinctive flavor.
	5	The competitive price.

Table 2

Summary of open-ended question from weakness analysis of Purchaser and Retailer.

WEAKNESS ANALYSIS		
Outlook from	Number	Statement
		The lack of information on the product marketing in turo-turo and online marketing.
		Skills in managerial activity is required for them to analyze financial problem.
		Lack of information from other financial institutions to finance the needs of the simple business.
		Comparison from turo-turo and online market can caused problems such as misunderstanding.
		Responsibility of finding committed co-workers.

Table 3

Summary of open-ended question from oppurtunities analysis of Purchaser and Retailer.

OPPURTUNITIES ANALYSIS		
Outlook from	Number	Statement
	1	Potential to get customer.
	2	Create new products.
	3	Socialize in the social media
	4	Create linkages with friends.
	5	Makes the retailer and purchaser exchange of ideas.

Table 4

Summary of open-ended question from threats analysis of Purchaser and Retailer.

THREATS ANALYSIS		
Outlook from	Number	Statement
	1	Competition of the price is highly presence.
	2	The survival of different association as a new competitor, or they provide protection only to certain entrepreneurs.
	3	Competitors with more employees can meet more customer's demands and more quickly access with
	4	The competition between turo-turo and online market is increased since a large population
	5	The big companies will create rivalry between the two.

Table 5

Summary of Selected Raw product available among Rizal Quirino Isabela in turo-turo

Purok 1	Purok 2
1. Saging(Banana)	1. Buko (Coconut)
2. Mais (Corn)	2. Ice Candy
3. Tuyoy(Dried Fish)	3. Halo halo
4. Red Egg (Salted Egg)	4. Marunggay (Malunggay)
5. Parya (Bitter Gourd)	5. Pinya (Pineapple)

Purok 4	Purok 5
1. Kamatis (Tomato)	1. Bildat
2. Tarong (Eggplant)	2. Kamote
3. Sinuuban (Smoked Fish)	3. Tugi (root crops)
4. Saluyot	4. Kankanen (native delicacy)
5. Balut	5. Carrot

As revealed by Table 5, that there is similarity from the foods being flog and that is the food is easily can grow and get from their surroundings. As expected turo-turo vendors focused on raw foods compared with online market. The research also found out that out of seven (7) purok four (4) of them has the so called turo-turo.

Table 6

Summary of Selected product available among Retailer in Online Market

Retailer 1	Retailer 2
1. Skin Soap	1. Summer Short
2. Lotion	2. Clothes
3. Lipstick	3. Underwear
4. Face Powder	4. Headband
5. Insect Repellant	5. Towel and Cycling

Retailer 3	Retailer 4
1. Diamond Necklace	1. Car Accessories
2. Wedding Ring	2. Laptop Accesories
3. Earing for men and women	3. Kitchen Utensils
4. Heads Accessories	4. Cellphone

5. Earing for kids

5. Printer

As revealed by Table 6, that there is variety from the selected product being vend and. As expected online marketing is a big change for the netizens to feel free what they want to sell as the researcher find out.

Generated Strategy of the Researcher

Established on the analysis performed by using SWOT analysis, competitive strategies are obtained. They can be used in the optimization of the owned resources and exploiting opportunities in every condition to reach the goal. The strategies are:

PR Strength Strategy

1. Maintaining the cleanliness and quality of the products in turo-turo like the raw materials while in internet the trust and rapport of the online user must maintain the openness of the purchaser.
2. Utilization of internet in Quirino, Isabela is sometimes creating connection lost.
3. Durability like clothes, shoes and materials things is an edge of the retailer.

PR Opportunities Strategy

1. A good quality and great competitiveness among online seller and turo-turo about the products.
2. The demand fulfillment of the quality products of the purchaser.

PR Weakness Strategy

1. Developing an equal partnership among turo-turo and online market.
2. Through training there is a need to upgrade the accessibility of competition.

PR Threats Strategy

1. The other agencies from the
2. Increasing the promotion team in order to reach more customers.

IV. Conclusions

The problems established by the turo-turo and online market is quiet create an issue because purchaser has always the right to choose more often observed that in turo-turo they sell raw materials such as foods while in online market is on material things. SWOT analysis is an effective way to measure the current status of the retailer in barrios hence this proved that creating a buzz in the industry is online popularity

though the essence of the product is standard and the spirit of competition is experienced.

Most of the turo-turos are traditionally grown and the availability of their product is easily captured in their surroundings. Thus, it is difficult for them to develop optimally due to the limited human resource quality. There are also obstacles in partnership efforts with the fact that the bigger entrepreneurs tend to dominate the decision making in pricing, product quality, as well as the payment system.

V. Recommendation

The strategies for the development of turo-turo and online market include the making of quality products that is supported by the product features that offer durability without compromising the healthy elements of the product itself like the kankanen of Ilokanos, so if a long-distance shipping or marketing is needed, then the product will still be in a good condition, and also developing an equal partnership and improving a harmonious coordination between the government and the businesses world to create an inventory media for various current issues related to business development.

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